

Supplementary File 1
Taking the temperature of punctuated equilibrium on its semicentennial
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Survey Instrument with Informed Consent Document

Informed Consent Document

INFORMED CONSENT FOR RESEARCH PROJECT TITLED:
Perceptions of Punctuated Equilibrium and Its Use in Teaching and Research

INTRODUCTION OF THE RESEARCHER:

My name is Margaret M. Yacobucci and I am a Professor of Geology in the School of Earth, Environment & Society at Bowling Green State University (BGSU). I am the Principal Investigator (PI) on this research project, which investigates how people think about the concept of punctuated equilibrium, how they use this concept in research, and how they teach about this concept. Anyone who is at least 18 years old and works or studies within paleontology or the biosciences is eligible to participate in this study.

PURPOSE:

The purpose of this research project is to examine how paleontologists and biologists think about the concept of punctuated equilibrium, first introduced in 1972 by Niles Eldredge and Stephen J. Gould. This project seeks to better understand how people define the concept of punctuated equilibrium and to what extent they use it in their research and teaching. General benefits of this research include adding to the bodies of knowledge around paleontological theory and the teaching of paleontology. Participants do not receive any direct benefit from participating.

PROCEDURE:

You will be asked to take an online survey, which should take about 10-15 minutes to complete. The survey can be taken or viewed on any device that can connect to the survey website.

VOLUNTARY NATURE:

The study adheres to current BGSU COVID-19 guidelines. Your participation is completely voluntary. You are free to withdraw at any time. You may decide to skip questions or discontinue participation at any time without explanation or penalty. Your decision whether or not to participate will not affect your relationship with Bowling Green State University or any other group or organization.

ANONYMITY PROTECTION:

The survey is anonymous, meaning that your responses do not include personally identifying information. All your survey responses will be kept on a secure online survey site called Qualtrics. I will download the survey data spreadsheet from the secure survey site. The full dataset will be stored on a Bowling Green State University campus password-protected computer and only I will have access to the data. Some employers may use tracking software, so participants may want to complete the survey on a personal computer. Participants should not leave the survey open if using a public computer or a computer that others may have access to. Participants should clear their browser cache and page history after completing the survey.

RISKS:

The risk of participation in this study is no greater than that experienced in daily life. As mentioned above, you are free to stop your participation in this study at any point, and I will take every possible precaution to safeguard your anonymity and ensure your privacy.

CONTACT INFORMATION:

If you have any questions about this research project or your participation in the research, please contact me, Dr. Margaret (Peg) M. Yacobucci, at 419-372-7982 or mmyacob@bgsu.edu. You may also contact the Chair of the Bowling Green State University Institutional Review Board, at 419-372-7716 or irb@bgsu.edu, if you have any questions about your rights as a participant in this research.

Thank you for your time in reviewing this consent form.

If you do NOT agree to participate in this research, please close this browser window.

SIGNATURE:

I have been informed of the purposes, procedures, risks and benefits of this study. I have had the opportunity to have all my questions answered and I have been informed that my participation is completely voluntary. By clicking on the arrow below, I agree to participate in this research.

Survey Instrument

1. On a scale of 1 to 4, how would you rate your current understanding of the concept of punctuated equilibrium/equilibria?
 - 1 – No understanding
 - 2 – Limited understanding
 - 3 – Average understanding
 - 4 – High level of understanding

2. Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements.
[1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Somewhat Disagree, 3 = Undecided, 4 = Somewhat Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree]

Punctuated equilibrium describes what allopatric (e.g., peripatric) speciation should look like as recorded in the fossil record

Anagenesis, in which an ancestral species transforms into a new species, is a common phenomenon

The fossil record is too imperfect for paleontology to contribute to evolutionary theory

New species evolve by the splitting of lineages

Most morphological change in a species happens during the speciation process

Punctuated equilibrium proposes non-Darwinian mechanisms of morphological evolution

The typical speciation process is relatively rapid because it involves a small population experiencing increased selection pressure, the effects of genetic drift, or becoming fixed at random for certain traits

Punctuated equilibrium states that morphological change occurs extremely rapidly (within a few generations) in the speciation process

The speciation process is typically completed within the first 1-10% of a species' total stratigraphic range

According to punctuated equilibrium, speciation is due to one or a few mutations that cause a sudden, large morphological change

Punctuated equilibrium has only rarely been documented in the fossil record

Species show little to no net morphological change (i.e., stasis) through most of their stratigraphic range

The pattern of punctuated equilibrium is a product of a limited fossil record and disappears when a high-resolution record is recovered

Punctuated equilibrium implies that species are evolutionary individuals with a defined birth, character suite, and death

3. On a scale of 1 to 10, how do you rate the importance of the concept of punctuated equilibrium to your field?

Slide bar from 0 to 10: 0 = Not At All Important to 10 = Extremely Important

4. How important is it for textbooks in your field to include coverage of punctuated equilibrium?
 - Not at all important – should not be included
 - Not very important

- Somewhat important – good to include
 - Very important – essential content
5. To what extent does your own research involve punctuated equilibrium?
- I do not conduct research
 - No involvement
 - A little involvement
 - Moderate involvement
 - Extensive involvement
6. Overall, in what percentage of the courses you teach do you discuss punctuated equilibrium?
Slide bar from 0% to 100% with Not Applicable / I Don't Teach option
7. In what contexts do you include punctuated equilibrium in your teaching? [Please select all that apply]
- I do not teach any courses
 - I include it in PK-12 courses
 - I include it in introductory-level courses for non-majors
 - I include it in introductory-level courses for majors
 - I include it in upper-level courses for majors
 - I include it in graduate-level courses
 - It is not relevant content for the courses I teach
8. Thinking just about the course in which you most discuss punctuated equilibrium, how much time do you devote to this concept?
- I do not teach courses
 - I teach courses but do not teach about punctuated equilibrium
 - I mention it only in passing
 - About 1 day
 - About 1 week
 - About 2 weeks
 - More than 2 weeks
9. What is your primary scientific discipline?
- Evolutionary biology (studying modern organisms)
 - Paleontology (studying fossil organisms)
 - Both equally
 - Other [if selected, text box opens with prompt to enter primary scientific discipline]
10. What type(s) of organisms do you primarily study? [Please select all that apply]
- Eubacteria/Archaea
 - Protists
 - Aquatic plants
 - Terrestrial plants
 - Fungi
 - Marine invertebrate animals
 - Freshwater invertebrate animals
 - Terrestrial invertebrate animals
 - Marine vertebrate animals
 - Freshwater vertebrate animals
 - Terrestrial vertebrate animals

11. Please indicate the discipline(s) in which you hold degree(s). [Please select all that apply]

	Biology / Biosciences	Geology / Geosciences	Other STEM field	Non-STEM field	I do not hold this degree
Undergraduate degree					
Master's degree					
Doctoral degree					

12. When did you receive your highest degree?

- Within the last 5 years
- 6 to 10 years ago
- 11 to 15 years ago
- 16 to 20 years ago
- More than 20 years ago

13. What is your current position / employment [Please select all that apply]

- Student
- Postdoctoral scholar
- PK-12 education
- 2-year college
- 4-year college (no or very few graduate programs)
- 4-year university (low or medium research intensity)
- 4-year university (high or very high research intensity)
- Museum, science center, other non-profit organization
- Government agency
- Industry / For-profit employer
- Retired

14. How much of your current position involves teaching?

Slide bar from 0% to 100%

15. Do you teach graduate-level courses?

- No
- Yes

16. Do you advise student researchers? [Please select all that apply]

- Yes, undergraduates
- Yes, Master's students
- Yes, doctoral students
- No

17. Have you ever TAKEN a university-level course in paleontology?

- No
- Yes

18. Have you ever TAKEN a university-level course in evolutionary biology?

- No
- Yes

19. Have you ever TAUGHT a university-level course in paleontology?

- No
- Yes

20. Have you ever TAUGHT a university-level course in evolutionary biology?

- No
- Yes

Thank you very much for completing this survey! Your survey responses have been recorded.